

DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF GRAPHITE-EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the dynamic stress-strain response of graphite epoxy composite laminates is investigated. The laminates are interposed in a section of a split Hopkinson apparatus. A quasi-rectangular wave is generated at one end of the incident bar by striking it with another bar of known length. This bar is accelerated using a compressed air gun. Approximate average stresses and strains can be obtained by measuring the incident, reflected and transmitted waves in the split bar. The dynamic behavior is evaluated for a range of impact velocities. The dependence of the response on impact velocity is analyzed and discussed.

Three different specimen thicknesses have been used. These are obtained by increasing the repetition factor of a base stacking sequence: (+45°, -45°, 0°, 90°). This process is called sublaminar scaling; it is preferred to ply scaling since it has been shown that the accumulation of layers of the same orientation decreases the failure load to such an extent that residual stresses may crack the specimen before any external load is applied. The laminates considered are: (+45°, -45°, 0°, 90°)_{ns}, n=2,3,4. The scale effects observed in the experimental response are analyzed and discussed.

Keywords: Split Hopkinson Bar, Impact, Sublaminar scaling.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper reports on the preliminary results of an ongoing research project on the dynamic through-the-thickness stress-strain response of graphite epoxy composite laminates. The results shown here will be complemented with those that are currently being obtained, and will be presented in poster form at the conference.

The somewhat low impact resistance of composite materials has limited the broad use of these materials in aircraft structures. There have been a great number of studies on the bending-type impact on plates or beams, but very few on the through-the-thickness response. When a small object strikes on a composite skin, the problem can be divided into two of different scales. The first is the propagation of compression waves perpendicular to the plate plane. The second is the bending of the laminate. The time required for the waves to travel the distance between the two outer surfaces of the plate is very short compared to the characteristic time for bending, therefore the two problems can be

analyzed independently. This work deals with the first type of response, the specimens are loaded with a plane wave traveling in a direction perpendicular to the laminate plane.

Composite materials also show interesting scaling effects that have been the subject of a number of studies. These effects need to be understood in order to be able to predict the behavior of the full scale structure from small prototypes, or from mathematical models that use properties measured on small laboratory coupons. Composite laminates show scaling effects that stem from the impossibility of scaling fiber diameter and ply thickness, and also from conflicts which prevent similitude in all relevant variables simultaneously. Sublaminar scaling is used in this study because, as has been pointed out, the accumulation of layers of the same orientation decreases the failure load to such an extent that residual stresses may crack the specimen before any external load is applied. This study addresses the scale effects by impacting specimens of three different thicknesses.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND BACKGROUND

2.1. Description and Instrumentation

The experimental setup is basically an air gun that impels a steel bar against the Split Bar where incident, reflected and transmitted waves can be measured. As will be commented on later, these measurements can be used to obtain an approximation of average strain and stress in the specimen. The schematics of the system is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Schematics of experimental setup.

The energy to accelerate the striker bar comes from a volume of air under pressure that has been stored in the chamber by an electric compressor. A valve, activated by a torque spring under load, is kept closed by a sliding fastener. When the spring is freed, the valve cracks open and lets the air escape. In its expansion, the air impels the striking bar against the split bar system. The incident velocity is measured by a counter that is activated when the striker traverses the (known) distance between two pairs of photo transistor-LED.

The moving bar strikes on the incident bar generating a strain wave that propagates towards the specimen. When the wave reaches the specimen section, it is decomposed into a compression wave that is transmitted through the specimen to the exit bar, and a tension wave that is reflected back at the end section of the incident bar. The Split System is shown in Figure 2. Strain gages 1, 2, and 3 register the waves as they traverse the section where they are located. The gages are connected in a quarter bridge arrangement. The signals from the bridges are magnified in a three channel amplifier and sent directly

to a dedicated computer or, to a digital oscilloscope and from here to the computer (Fig. 1). This second route is sometimes necessary because the data acquisition board sampling rate is not high enough to capture the waves accurately. When the first route is used, the LabVIEW software was the tool to perform the data acquisition as well as the data processing and plotting.

Fig. 2. Schematics of Hopkinson bars and instrumentation.

2.2. Background to the Split Hopkinson Bar

The theory of one-dimensional longitudinal waves is capable of estimating the dynamic stress-strain response of the specimen. A brief derivation of the formulae follows. Gage 1 measures the incident wave ϵ_i , that is, the strain wave that travels towards the specimen in the first stages of the impact process. Gage 2 measures the sum of incident plus reflected waves. By looking at Figure 2 it can be inferred that this is not true for a short period of time, at the arrival of the incident wave, when only ϵ_i is being measured, that is, when no interference has yet taken place. Also, when the recording time is large, all gages measurements are a consequence of multiple interference from which no useful information can be obtained.

In general, the displacement of an arbitrary section is the sum of two waves traveling in opposite directions:

$$u = f(x - c_0t) + g(x + c_0t) \quad (1)$$

The derivative of Equation 1 with respect to x provides the incident and reflected strain waves. On the other hand, differentiation with respect to time yields the velocity of the section at hand as a function of strain. Thus, the displacements of the incident and exit sections of the specimen are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} u_1 &= c_0 \int_0^t (-\epsilon_i + \epsilon_r) dt \\ u_2 &= -c_0 \int_0^t \epsilon_t dt \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The average strain in the specimen at time t is:

$$\epsilon_s = \frac{u_2 - u_1}{l_0} = -\frac{2c_0}{l_0} \int_0^t \epsilon_t dt \quad (3)$$

And if the specimen inertia is neglected:

$$P_1 = AE(\epsilon_i + \epsilon_r) = P_2 = AE\epsilon_t \Rightarrow \sigma_s = \frac{A}{A_s} E\epsilon_t \quad (4)$$

The origin for time is taken to be the instant when the incident wave reaches the specimen section. This is also the time instant in which the reflected wave starts to travel and, since the specimen thickness has been neglected, it is also the starting time for the transmitted wave. Therefore, the incident, transmitted and reflected waves are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_i(t) &= \epsilon_i(t' - t'_1) \\ \epsilon_t(t) &= \epsilon_3(t' - t'_3) \\ \epsilon_i(t) &= \epsilon_2\left(t' - t'_2 - \frac{0.1}{c_0}\right) - \epsilon_1\left(t' - t'_1 - \frac{0.1}{c_0}\right)\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

Where t' is the time coordinate with origin at the beginning of the recording process. Parameter t'_1 (t'_2) is the arrival time of the incident wave to the section where gage 1 (gage 2) is located. Likewise, t'_3 is the arrival time of the transmitted wave to the section where gage 3 is located. The factor $0.1/c_0$ is the time required for the wave to travel from gage 2 to the end of the incident bar and back.

Sample waves are shown in Figure 3. Figure 3a shows the waves as recorded by gages 1, 2, and 3. The arrival times of the different waves at each gage section is marked in the figure. The features pointed out in previous paragraphs can be clearly seen in this figure. It can also be noted that waves ϵ_2 and ϵ_3 converge for times greater than t'_3 . The reason for this is that the specimen section is at the midpoint between these two gages. The reduction of these data according to the formulae in (5) yields the incident, reflected and transmitted waves (Figure 3b). The maximum time for which the expressions in (5) are valid is that in which the reflected wave reaches the section of gage 1. That is:

$$t'_{\max} = t'_1 + \frac{0.9}{c_0} \quad t_{\max} = \frac{0.9}{c_0}$$

For times less or equal to this value, the average strain and stress in the specimen are given by (4) and (5), respectively. The sample curves can be seen in Figure 3c.

Fig. 3. Recorded waves (a), incident, reflected and transmitted waves (b), average stress and strain in the specimen (c).

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The waves generated in the bars were recorded from the three gages and treated according to the data

reduction process described in the previous section.

Stiffness.

The stress-strain curves obtained are shown in Figure 4. It can be seen that, for all three sizes, the apparent through-the-thickness stiffness varies in a non-monotonic fashion with the incident velocity. As mentioned in the introduction this result is based on a preliminary study, further research is required to clarify this unusual behavior. Some hypothesis are being stressed at the moment. On the one hand, it could be due to inherent material non-linearities. On the other hand, the scatter could be due to specimen-bar contact problems. That is, the initial contact pressure could influence the apparent stiffness and obscure the effect of the incident velocity. In order to study this last idea it is necessary to provide the impact system with a device to measure initial clamping load.

Fig. 4. Stress-strain curves for thin (a), medium (b) and thick specimens.

It has been observed that the results are influenced by slight modifications of the wave arrival time at each gage location. This is a critical point in the data reduction process. An attempt was made to automate this process by considering that the front wave was at the gage location when the measured voltage was, say, 5% of the maximum recorded voltage. This process yielded worse results than the "manual" counterpart because visual interpretation can make the wave fronts coincide more accurately.

Failure.

Failure occurs at a critical energy (or speed, since the incident bar weight is fixed), dependent on the specimen size. The critical speed (energy) for the thin specimens (n=2) is 27 m/s (321 J). The thick specimens (n=4) failed at a speed (energy) level of 30 m/s (396 J). And the mid-size specimens failed at an intermediate speed (energy) level of 29 m/s (370 J). Simple algebra yields the scale factor for the critical energy level:

$$\frac{E_i}{E_4} = \lambda^x, \quad x \approx 0.3$$

Where λ is the geometrical scale factor. The value of $x=0.3$ is a surprising result that needs to be con-

firmed. One would expect the energy to scale as does the volume of the specimen (λ^1 in this case, where only the thickness has been scaled).

For energy levels below the critical level, the specimens suffer no apparent damage. On the other hand, for energy levels above or equal to the critical level, the specimens suffer severe damage and are practically pulverized after impact. This phenomenon has been observed in other types of impact and has been reported in many occasions. In this case, despite the fact that there is a severe scatter in apparent stiffness for different values of incident energy, the critical energy is an accurately determined value only dependent on the scale factor.

Average.

If the stiffness dependence on velocity is considered as experimental scatter, then it is necessary to obtain average curves for each scale factor in order to extract meaningful comparisons between sizes. These average curves are plotted in Figure 5. It can be seen that the apparent stiffness of the thick specimens is higher than the corresponding average stiffness of the thin specimens. The mid-size specimens show an intermediate value for the apparent stiffness. This scale effect is of the same polarity of that observed for three-point-bending impact loading of composite beams.

Fig. 5. Average stress-strain curves for all three sizes.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Preliminary results on the scale effects and impact responses of composite laminates have been presented. It has been shown that damage occurs for incident energy levels higher than a critical value that depends on the scale factor. The stiffness varies with incident velocity in a non-monotonic way. Average values of stiffness show, again, a scale effect: larger specimens are stiffer than the small ones. This results need further confirmation, experiments in this direction are underway.

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